

Activated alumina ball catalyzed expeditious synthesis of 2-alkylbenzimidazoles with special emphasis on susceptible side chains possessing amide functionality[†]

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Abstract : A solvent- and chromatography-free, non-hazardous green protocol for the synthesis of 2-alkylbenzimidazoles has been developed under neutral conditions with water as the only by-product. Activated alumina balls, which have been shown previously to assist in amidation reaction, also catalyze very successfully the condensation of benzene-1,2-diamines with carboxylic acids to produce the corresponding benzimidazoles. This methodology is also applicable to susceptible side chains possessing an amide functionality.

Keywords : 2-Alkylbenzimidazoles, green protocol, neutral conditions, non-hazardous, solvent-free.

Introduction

2-Substituted benzimidazoles exhibit biological activities such as antiulcer, antiviral and antitumor effects. A general viable method for high-throughput synthesis of the benzimidazole scaffold is thus of immense value in a drug discovery process¹⁻⁵. There is a ubiquitous presence of the benzimidazole scaffold in a wide range of bioactive molecules and is considered to be a privileged sub-structure for drug design⁶.

Recently, we had investigated amidation reaction of carboxylic acids and amines utilizing cheap and easily available alumina balls as a heterogeneous catalyst after activation, in the one-step synthesis of amide functionality leading to non-hazardous metal-free protocol⁷. In our current methodology, we have utilized these same alumina balls in a direct condensation reaction to form benzimidazoles, the only side product being water. The direct condensation to form benzimidazoles avoids poor atom economy and step economy. Moreover, the use of alumina balls as heterogeneous catalyst in assisting benzimidazole synthesis leads to a very clean reaction unlike the HPF₆-catalyzed benzimidazole synthesis developed by

us⁸ or the conventional synthesis of benzimidazoles involving heating the reactants in refluxing aqueous hydrochloric acid⁹ or in slurry of the dehydrating agent polyphosphoric acid¹⁰. From the environmental and economic point of view, the end of life prospects for the alumina ball catalyst are simple and can be disposed with minimal preparation. Such direct condensation with an inexpensive heterogeneous catalyst is always desired which results in easy procurement of the components to synthesize a technologically and biochemically important core such as benzimidazole. In this work, we demonstrate the first example of a heterogeneously catalyzed reaction of carboxylic acids with benzene-1,2-diamines to form benzimidazole and H₂O using the easily available simple activated alumina ball catalyst after calcination and in the absence of any potentially harmful inorganic acid catalyst⁸⁻¹⁰.

Results and discussion

When activated alumina balls successfully catalyzed the amide synthesis with carboxylic acid and amine⁷, we wanted to see if we can take the reaction a step further and tried a condensation with the same carboxylic acid

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Table 1. Synthesis of 2-hexyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (**7gd**, Table 2b)

Catalyst	Calcination temp. (°C)	Catalyst loading (wt%)	Conversion (%) ^b
None	-	-	0
Zeolite	700	0/10/20	0/0/0
Alumina (neutral)	-	0/10/20	0/0/0
Alumina (neutral)	700	0/10/20/50	0/0/0/0
Alumina balls ^c	-	0/10/50	0/50/50
Alumina balls ^c	120	5/10/20/50	35/63/63/63
Alumina balls ^c	400	5/10/20	65/90/90
Alumina balls ^c	700	5/10/20	70/93/93

^a0–50 wt% of catalyst in relation to total mass of reagents (exact catalyst loading mentioned in column 3 of the table), neat reaction conditions at 150 °C (the reaction does not take place at room temperature and this optimum temperature is required for the reaction to take place) for 5 h, 10 mmol of heptanoic acid and 10 mmol of benzene-1,2-diamine. ^bIsolated yield. ^cActivated alumina balls from Sorbead India.

benzimidazole formation. The catalytic activity of zeolite was also tested but to no avail. We steered clear of all acidic catalysts as the presence of such catalysts lead to hydrolysis, as mentioned above. The maximum yield of 2-hexyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (**7gd**) at 93% is obtained with the alumina balls calcined at 700 °C. At 400 °C calcination of the alumina balls, the maximum yield of **7gd** (90%) was similar. The isolated yield increases to a very large extent (63% to 90%) on calcination of the alumina balls from 120 °C to 400 °C. Room temperature-activated alumina balls produce 50% yield of compound **7gd** under optimized reaction conditions. Fig. 2 gives the variation of this compound **7gd** with the calcination temperature of the catalyst. This is a solvent-free and chromatography-free protocol for benzimidazole synthesis and hence the use of volatile organic solvents is limited to a minimum. Water remained as the only by-product. Unreacted carboxylic acid and benzene-1,2-diamine remained in trace quantities. The pure product was obtained by recrystallization. The percentage of carbon in the reactants that is incorporated into the final product benzimidazole i.e. carbon balance is 100%.

The 2-alkylbenzimidazoles (**5**, **7**) formed using the above optimized conditions with benzene-1,2-diamines (**4**) and carboxylic acids (**3**, **6**) are listed in Table 2a and Table 2b. The acids **3a**, **3b** and **3c** were prepared by

Fig. 2. Variation of isolated yield of 2-*n*-hexyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (**7gd**, Table 2b) with change in calcination temperature of the catalyst alumina ball.

refluxing succinic anhydride (**2**) with piperidine (**1a**), morpholine (**1b**) and pyrrolidine (**1c**) (Scheme 1). These sensitive functionalised acids were then reacted with the corresponding amines (**4**) in the presence of activated alumina balls to form the corresponding benzimidazole in compounds **5ad**, **5ae**, **5be**, **5cf**, **5ce** and **5cd** in considerable yields.

The activated alumina ball catalyst showed high activity for condensation of the benzene-1,2-diamines and

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the desired benzimidazoles with susceptible side chains.

Table 2a. Synthesized benzimidazoles with susceptible side chains using alumina ball catalyst^{a,b}

Entry	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Benzimidazole 5
1	H	H		 5ad (81%) ¹²
2	CH ₃	CH ₃		 5ae (85%)
3	CH ₃	CH ₃		 5be (90%)
4	H	CH ₃		 5cf (75%)
5	CH ₃	CH ₃		 5ce (80%)
6	H	H		 5cd (78%)

^aReaction conditions : **3** (10 mmol), **4** (10 mmol), alumina balls (10 wt% in relation to total mass of reagents), neat reaction, 150 °C, 5 h.

^bIsolated yields based on **3**.

the carboxylic acids. The ball structure with particular aggregated particle morphology of alumina is responsible

for the high catalytic activity in these reactions. The reaction shows good results irrespective of the structure of the reactants. A minimum of around 72% yield is reached in the cases studied. As in the case of amidation reaction⁷, the highly porous and aggregated particle nature of these activated alumina balls (Experimental, SEM images, Fig. S1, powder XRD, Fig. 3 and the porosimetry data in Table 3, Figs. 4–8) is responsible for these high yielding reactions. The different calcination temperature of alumina ball lead to various catalytic activity. The particle aggregates change shape from *spherical* to *rhombohedral* on calcination from 120 °C to 700 °C resulting in the increased activity of the catalyst. The BET surface area (by nitrogen adsorption at 77 K) decreases on increasing the activation temperature from 120 °C, 400 °C and 700 °C. The pore volume (0.3635 cc g⁻¹) and pore width (10.8 nm) is maximum at 700 °C activation temperature. This high pore width and pore volume favours easy diffusion of the reactant and product molecules during the reaction. When the calcined alumina spheres adsorb the excess water, one of the products is removed from the reaction media and the reaction equilibrium constantly moves towards the formation of benzimidazole. The plausible mechanism for the benzimidazole formation is given in Scheme 2. The surface area (87.95 m² g⁻¹) and pore volume (0.1675 cc g⁻¹) of neutral alumina is low when compared to that of the alumina ball even at room temperature (255.17 m² g⁻¹ surface area and 0.3140 cc g⁻¹ pore volume). As the activity is dependent on the

Table 2b. Synthesized benzimidazoles (general) using alumina ball catalyst^{a,b}

Entry	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Benzimidazole 7
1	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₅	 7ge (93%) ⁸
2	H	H	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₅	 7gd (93%) ¹³
3	H	H	CH ₃	 7hd (90%) ¹⁴
4	CH ₃	CH ₃		 7ie (90%) ⁸
5	CH ₃	CH ₃		 7ge (72%) ⁸
6	H	CH ₃		 7kf (73%) ⁸
7	H	H	H	 7ld (92%) ¹⁵
8	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	 7hf (93%) ^{c,16}
9	H	H	(CH ₂) ₂ CH ₃	 7md (90%) ¹⁷
10	H	CH ₃	(CH ₂) ₂ CH ₃	 7mf (89%) ¹⁸
11	CH ₃	CH ₃	(CH ₂) ₂ CH ₃	 7me (95%) ¹⁵

Table-2b (contd.)				
12	H	CH ₃	CH(CH ₂ CH ₃)Ph	
13	CH ₃	CH ₃	(CH ₂) ₃ (3-indolyl)	
14	Cl	Cl	CH ₃	
15	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₂ Ph	

^aReaction conditions : **4** (10 mmol), **6** (10 mmol), alumina balls (10 wt% in relation to total mass of reagents), neat reaction, 150 °C, 5 h.
^bIsolated yields based on **6**. ^cReaction was recorded on a 10 mmol scale and also a 100 mmol scale with similar isolated yields.

Fig. 3. Wide angle powdered XRD patterns of the alumina ball calcined at 120 °C (a); the alumina ball at RT (b); neutral alumina (c); the alumina ball calcined at 700 °C (d) and the alumina ball calcined at 400 °C (e).

ball form of alumina calcined at different temperatures, powder XRD patterns remained almost same. These alumina balls are neutral catalysts and hence protonation of the benzene-1,2-diamines does not occur to give an inactive salt. A scale-up reaction was also studied (Table 2b, product **7hf**) on a 100 mmol scale with 93% isolated yield. The synthesized aliphatic functionalized acids **3a**, **3b** and **3c** could survive the present reaction conditions indicating the mildness of the activated alumina balls. The benzimidazole **7je** is also biologically active in hu-

Scheme 2. The potential mechanism of benzimidazole formation in presence of activated alumina ball.

man histiocytic lymphoma cell-line U937 with an IC₅₀ value of 11.7⁸.

In order to check the reusability of the activated alumina ball catalyst for this present methodology on benzimidazole synthesis, we take the reaction of simple benzene-1,2-diamine and heptanoic acid to form 2-*n*-hexyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (**7gd**) as the model reaction. The crude reaction mixture was dissolved in dichloromethane and filtered. The alumina balls were further washed and dried under vacuum. The reusability of the catalyst was then checked. Even without activation further to 120 °C or

Fig. 4. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm of the alumina ball at RT. Pore size distributions estimated through NLDFT method is shown in the inset. BET surface area of this RT sample is 255.17 m² g⁻¹. Pore width 5.64 nm; Pore volume 0.3140 cc g⁻¹.

Fig. 6. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm of the alumina ball calcined at 400 °C. Pore size distributions estimated through NLDFT method is shown in the inset. BET surface area of the alumina ball calcined at 400 °C sample is 230.72 m² g⁻¹. Pore width 6.03 nm; Pore volume 0.3614 cc g⁻¹.

Fig. 5. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm of the alumina ball calcined at 120 °C. Pore size distributions estimated through NLDFT method is shown in the inset. BET surface area of the alumina ball calcined at 120 °C sample is 245.31 m² g⁻¹. Pore width 5.6 nm; Pore volume 0.3136 cc g⁻¹.

Fig. 7. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm of the alumina ball calcined at 700 °C. Pore size distributions estimated through NLDFT method is shown in the inset. BET surface area of the alumina ball calcined at 700 °C sample is 121.84 m² g⁻¹. Pore width 10.8 nm; Pore volume 0.3635 cc g⁻¹.

better still at 700 °C, an isolated yield of 78% is obtained after the first use (Table 4). A maximum of 81% yield is obtained after the third use of these alumina balls after

reactivating to 700 °C. Since the separation of the catalyst from the reaction medium and its further reuse is a

Table 3. The summarised porosimetry data as obtained from N₂ physisorption method

	BET surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	Pore width (nm)	Pore volume (cc g ⁻¹)
Neutral alumina	87.95	8.18	0.1675
RT alumina ball	255.17	5.68	0.3140
120 °C activated alumina ball	245.31	5.6	0.3136
400 °C activated alumina ball	230.72	6.03	0.3614
700 °C activated alumina ball	121.84	10.8	0.3635

Fig. 8. N_2 adsorption/desorption isotherm of neutral alumina. Pore size distributions estimated through NLDFT method is shown in the inset. BET surface area of neutral alumina sample is $87.95 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. Pore width 8.18 nm ; Pore volume 0.1675 cc g^{-1} .

Table 4. Effect of reuse on yield of 2-*n*-hexyl-1*H*-benzimidazole, **7gd**^{a,b}

Reactivation temperature	Yield (%) ^c		
	1st use	2nd use	3rd use
CH_2Cl_2 wash (vacuum dried)	78	72	63
120 °C	84	80	75
700 °C	90	87	81

^aReaction conditions as in Table 2. ^bThere was no loss of catalyst on transfer due to the macroscopic "ball" nature of the catalyst. ^cRecrystallized isolated yield.

very important step in both industry and academia alike, our alumina ball catalyst for benzimidazole synthesis is easily available, very cheap (thus cutting down the cost of the total synthesis which is a very important step from the industry point of view), macroscopic, heterogeneous and hence can be filtered off from the reaction media without the need for centrifuge and without much loss or difficulty for further reuse.

The change in isolated yield of compound **7gd** with time was also checked (Table 5) by leaving the catalyst exposed to air for up to a month. A decrease in yield from 93% to 75% is observed while 75% yield is obtained on reactivation of the catalyst to 700 °C. Without reactivation the yield is 66% after air exposure for a month. After a minimum of 12 h exposure, the yield is

Table 5. Change in isolated yield of 2-*n*-hexyl-1*H*-benzimidazole, **7gd**^{a,b}

	Time of exposure in air			
	12 h	24 h	1 week	1 month
Unactivated catalyst	87	84	78	66
Activated catalyst (700 °C)	90	87	81	75

^aReaction conditions as in Table 2. ^bRecrystallized isolated yield given under each column.

90% and 87% with and without pre-treatment of the alumina ball catalyst to 700 °C. Thus, the activated alumina balls required for our benzimidazole synthesis do get deactivated on atmospheric exposure, but not to an extent to completely lose its reaction enhancing properties.

Based on the concept of established green chemistry metrics¹⁹, we calculated the metrics for a representative benzimidazole **5ad** (Table 6). We observe that the ratio of waste to product, i.e. *E*-factor is only 0.14. Mass intensity, which should ideally approach 1, is actually 1.55.

Table 6. Calculation of green metrics

3-(1 <i>H</i> -Benzimidazol-2-yl)-1-(piperidin-1-yl)propanamide (5ad)	<i>E</i> -factor	Mass intensity	Atom economy
	0.14	1.55	88%

Atom economy is 88%. As the green metrics are not too way off the ideal mark, our present methodology is an example of a clean synthetic route for benzimidazole synthesis.

Conclusions

The condensation of benzene-1,2-diamines was achieved in presence of activated alumina balls, producing benzimidazoles. The alumina ball catalyst develops unique morphology with increase of calcination temperature leading to increase in the product yield. Additionally, the reactions can be performed under solvent-free and chromatography-free conditions, rendering this protocol to synthesize benzimidazoles highly beneficial from environmental and economical point of view. The use of alumina balls to catalyse benzimidazole synthesis opens up another practical application of this novel alumina catalyst in addition to amidation reaction⁷.

Experimental

General information : Benzimidazoles were synthe-

sized under neat reaction conditions at 150 °C and an air atmosphere. The typical quantities used were 10 mmol of acid, 10 mmol of corresponding benzene-1,2-diamine, and varying quantities of activated alumina ball catalyst. NMR spectra were obtained on a 300 MHz Bruker spectrometer (400 MHz Bruker spectrometer was used in case of **5ce**, obtaining its 2D NMR spectra) using CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆ solvent.

General procedure for benzimidazole synthesis : 3-(1*H*-Benzoimidazol-2-yl)-1-piperidin-1-ylpropan-1-one (**5ad**) : 4-Oxo-4-piperidin-1-yl-butyric acid (1.85 g, 10 mmol), benzene-1,2-diamine (1.08 g, 10 mmol) and activated alumina balls calcined at 700 °C (0.29 g) were heated to 150 °C in a round bottomed flask. After 5 h the hot reaction mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate and filtered through a sintered glass funnel, the catalyst was washed with 20 ml of hot ethyl acetate and dried under vacuum. Yield obtained for 3-(1*H*-benzoimidazol-2-yl)-1-piperidin-1-ylpropan-1-one : 2.08 g (81%).

Benzimidazole analytical data :

3-(1*H*-Benzoimidazol-2-yl)-1-piperidin-1-ylpropanamide (**5ad**, Table 2a, entry 1) : Off-white solid; m.p. 72 °C (EtOAc); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 9.21 (1H, br s, NH), 7.42–7.39 (2H, m, Ar), 7.05–7.02 (2H, m, Ar), 3.40–3.38 (2H, m), 3.20 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 3.12–3.09 (2H, m), 2.80 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 1.41–1.26 (6H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 169.5, 154.3, 137.9, 121.4, 114.0, 45.8, 42.4, 30.5, 25.5, 24.9, 24.0, 23.7; IR (KBr) : 3195, 1623, 1449 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₉N₃O : C, 70.01; H, 7.44; N, 16.33 and Found : C, 70.00; H, 7.42; N, 16.35.

3-(5,6-Dimethyl-1*H*-benzoimidazol-2-yl)-1-piperidin-1-ylpropanamide (**5ae**, Table 2a, entry 2) : Off-white solid; m.p. 206 °C (MeOH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.84 (1H, br s, NH), 7.17 (2H, s, Ar), 3.39–3.36 (4H, m), 2.96–2.91 (2H, m), 2.80–2.75 (2H, m), 2.23 (6H, s, CH₃), 1.53–1.36 (6H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 169.2, 153.6, 129.4, 45.8, 42.1, 30.4, 26.0, 25.3, 24.3, 24.1, 20.0; IR (KBr) : 2932, 1632, 1450 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₂₃N₃O : C, 71.55; H, 8.12; N, 14.72 and Found : C, 71.58; H, 8.12; N, 14.71.

3-(5,6-Dimethyl-1*H*-benzoimidazol-2-yl)-1-morpholin-4-ylpropanamide (**5be**, Table 2a, entry 3) : Off-white solid; m.p. 210 °C (MeOH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.86 (1H, br s, NH), 7.20–7.14 (2H, m, Ar),

3.50–3.39 (8H, m), 2.98–2.93 (2H, m), 2.83–2.78 (2H, m), 2.23 (6H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 170.0, 153.5, 66.2, 45.4, 41.6, 30.1, 24.2, 20.0; IR (KBr) : 3236, 1617, 1465, 1438 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₁N₃O₂ : C, 66.88; H, 7.37; N, 14.62 and Found : C, 66.88; H, 7.36; N, 14.65.

3-(6-Methyl-1*H*-benzoimidazol-2-yl)-1-pyrrolidin-1-ylpropanamide (**5cf**, Table 2a, entry 4) : Sticky brown mass; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar), 7.25 (1H, s, Ar), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar), 3.42 (2H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 3.26 (2H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz), 3.02 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.78 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.43 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.90–1.70 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 169.3, 153.7, 130.3, 122.6, 114.5, 114.0, 45.9, 45.4, 31.7, 26.7, 25.7, 24.0, 21.3; IR (KBr) : 3198, 1634, 1453 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₉N₃O : C, 70.01; H, 7.44; N, 16.33 and Found : C, 70.00; H, 7.41; N, 16.32.

3-(5,6-Dimethyl-1*H*-benzoimidazol-2-yl)-1-pyrrolidin-1-ylpropanamide (**5ce**, Table 2a, entry 5) : Off-white solid; m.p. 150 °C (MeOH); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.89 (1H, br s, NH), 7.21 (2H, s, Ar), 3.45–3.38 (4H, m), 3.28–3.25 (2H, m), 2.98 (1H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz), 2.76 (1H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz), 2.52–2.49 (2H, m), 2.27 (6H, s, CH₃), 1.88–1.83 (1H, m), 1.79–1.72 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 169.3, 153.6, 153.1, 45.8, 45.3, 31.7, 26.7, 25.6, 24.0, 23.8, 19.9; IR (KBr) : 3197, 1636, 1455 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₁N₃O : C, 70.82; H, 7.80; N, 15.49 and Found : C, 70.83; H, 7.81; N, 15.49.

3-(1*H*-Benzoimidazol-2-yl)-1-pyrrolidin-1-ylpropanamide (**5cd**, Table 2a, entry 6) : Off-white solid; m.p. above 260 °C (MeOH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.32–12.11 (1H, m, NH), 7.42 (2H, br s, Ar), 7.08–7.05 (2H, m, Ar), 3.42–3.21 (6H, m), 2.99 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.75 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.46–2.45 (2H, m), 1.88–1.79 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 169.3, 154.0, 121.2, 45.8, 45.3, 31.6, 26.6, 25.6, 24.0; IR (KBr) : 3196, 1634, 1455 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₇N₃O : C, 69.11; H, 7.04; N, 17.27 and Found : C, 69.10; H, 7.05; N, 17.27.

2-*n*-Hexyl-5,6-dimethyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (**7ge**, Table 2b, entry 1) : Sticky solid; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 12.71 (1H, s, NH), 7.25 (2H, s, Ar), 2.86 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 2.22 (6H, s), 1.79–1.69 (2H, m), 1.20–1.05 (6H, m), 0.75 (3H, br s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) :

δ 155.2, 137.0, 130.6, 114.7, 31.4, 29.2, 29.0, 28.5, 22.4, 20.1, 13.8; IR (KBr) : 2927, 1451, 1020 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2$: C, 78.21; H, 9.63; N, 12.16 and Found : C, 78.21; H, 9.61; N, 12.15.

2-n-Hexyl-1H-benzimidazole (7gd, Table 2b, entry 2) : Brown solid; m.p. 138 °C (EtOAc); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 7.34–7.29 (2H, m, Ar), 7.01–6.95 (2H, m, Ar), 2.71 (2H, t, J 7.8 Hz), 1.67–1.57 (2H, m), 1.18–0.98 (6H, m), 0.60 (3H, t, J 6.9 Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 155.4, 137.8, 122.3, 114.4, 31.4, 28.9, 28.2, 22.4, 13.9; IR (KBr) : 2927, 1418, 1273, 751 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$: C, 77.18; H, 8.97; N, 13.85 and Found : C, 77.19; H, 8.99; N, 13.84.

2-Methyl-1H-benzimidazole (7hd, Table 2b, entry 3) : Brown solid; m.p. 175–176 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.57–7.51 (2H, m, Ar), 7.42 (1H, br s, NH), 7.24–7.19 (2H, m, Ar), 2.65 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 151.2, 138.6, 122.2, 114.5, 14.9; IR (KBr) : 2673, 1384, 1267, 732 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$: C, 72.70; H, 6.10; N, 21.20 and Found : C, 72.70; H, 6.12; N, 21.20.

2-Cyclopropyl-5,6-dimethyl-1H-benzimidazole (7ie, Table 2b, entry 4) : Light brown solid; m.p. 220 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 11.86 (1H, br s, NH), 7.12 (2H, s, Ar), 2.22 (6H, s, CH_3), 2.03–1.98 (1H, m), 0.97–0.93 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 155.9, 129.0, 117.8, 19.9, 9.5, 8.5; IR (KBr) : 2896, 1437, 1307, 998, 853 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2$: C, 77.38; H, 7.58; N, 15.04 and Found : C, 77.39; H, 7.60; N, 15.03.

5,6-Dimethyl-2-(naphthalen-1-yl)methyl-1H-benzimidazole (7je, Table 2b, entry 5) : Light brown solid; m.p. 218 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 11.90 (1H, br s, NH), 8.17–8.14 (1H, m, Ar), 7.90–7.87 (1H, m, Ar), 7.82–7.80 (1H, m, Ar), 7.48–7.42 (4H, m, Ar), 7.17 (2H, s, Ar), 4.55 (2H, s), 2.22 (6H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 152.5, 133.9, 133.5, 131.7, 129.5, 128.5, 127.34, 127.28, 126.2, 125.8, 125.7, 124.1, 32.8, 19.9; IR (KBr) : 2923, 1448, 1012, 781 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$: C, 83.88; H, 6.34; N, 9.78 and Found : C, 83.86; H, 6.35; N, 9.79.

2-(1H-Indol-3-yl)methyl-6-methyl-1H-benzimidazole (7kf, Table 2b, entry 6) : Grey solid; m.p. 90 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 11.03 (1H, s, NH),

7.41–7.32 (4H, m, Ar), 7.07–7.01 (3H, m, Ar), 6.91 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 4.37 (2H, s), 2.37 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 154.0, 136.3, 130.2, 127.0, 123.7, 122.5, 121.1, 118.49, 118.46, 111.4, 110.1, 25.4, 21.3; IR (KBr) : 3392, 742 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3$: C, 78.13; H, 5.79; N, 16.08 and Found : C, 78.13; H, 5.78; N, 16.09.

1H-Benzimidazole : Brown solid (7ld, Table 2b, entry 7) : m.p. 170 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 8.18 (1H, s), 7.56–7.54 (2H, m, Ar), 7.15–7.12 (2H, m, Ar); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 142.1, 138.2, 121.9, 115.4; IR (KBr) : 2793, 1407, 1245, 744 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2$: C, 71.17; H, 5.12; N, 23.71 and Found : C, 71.17; H, 5.11; N, 23.70.

2,6-Dimethyl-1H-benzimidazole (7hf, Table 2b, entry 8) : Brown solid; m.p. 202 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.92 (1H, br s, NH), 7.45 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar), 7.34 (1H, s, Ar), 7.05 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar), 2.63 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.44 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 151.0, 138.1, 136.7, 132.0, 123.7, 114.2, 113.9, 21.5, 14.7; IR (KBr) : 2918, 1450, 1400, 1281, 1027, 801 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2$: C, 73.94; H, 6.89; N, 19.16 and Found : C, 73.94; H, 6.89; N, 19.17.

2-n-Propyl-1H-benzimidazole (7md, Table 2b, entry 9) : Brown solid; m.p. 160–162 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.94 (1H, br s, NH), 7.61–7.58 (2H, m, Ar), 7.28–7.24 (2H, m, Ar), 2.98 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 1.99–1.87 (2H, m), 1.00 (3H, t, J 7.5 Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 155.0, 137.7, 122.5, 114.5, 30.9, 21.6, 13.8; IR (KBr) : 2958, 1427, 1268, 745 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2$: C, 74.97; H, 7.55; N, 17.48 and Found : C, 74.98; H, 7.56; N, 17.47.

6-Methyl-2-n-propyl-1H-benzimidazole (7mf, Table 2b, entry 10) : Light brown solid; m.p. 153–154 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 9.08 (1H, br s, NH), 7.44 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar), 7.33 (1H, s, Ar), 7.04 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar), 2.90 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 2.44 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 1.94–1.81 (2H, m), 0.97 (3H, t, J 7.5 Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 155.1, 138.4, 137.0, 131.8, 123.4, 114.4, 114.1, 31.2, 21.7, 21.6, 13.8; IR (KBr) : 2959, 1446, 1281, 798 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2$: C, 75.82; H, 8.10; N, 16.08 and Found : C, 75.81; H, 8.11; N, 16.08.

5,6-Dimethyl-2-*n*-propyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (7me, Table 2b, entry 11) : Light brown solid; m.p. 167 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.86 (1H, br s, NH), 7.17 (2H, s, Ar), 2.68 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 2.23 (6H, s, Ar-CH₃), 1.77–1.67 (2H, m), 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 154.1, 137.2, 129.4, 114.6, 30.9, 21.5, 20.3, 14.1; IR (KBr) : 2970, 1454, 1406, 1304, 1002, 852 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₆N₂ : C, 76.55; H, 8.57; N, 14.88 and Found : C, 76.55; H, 8.57; N, 14.89.

6-Methyl-2-(1-phenyl-*n*-propyl)-1*H*-benzimidazole (7nf, Table 2b, entry 12) : Brown solid; m.p. 120 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.88 (1H, br s, NH), 7.43 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar), 7.33–7.14 (6H, m, Ar), 7.04 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar), 4.14 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 2.52–2.42 (4H, m), 2.32–2.11 (1H, m), 0.93 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 156.3, 140.7, 137.3, 135.9, 132.5, 128.8, 128.0, 127.2, 124.1, 114.6, 114.2, 47.8, 27.5, 21.5, 12.3; IR (KBr) : 2928, 1449, 1278, 807, 697 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₈N₂ : C, 81.56; H, 7.25; N, 11.19 and Found : C, 81.57; H, 7.26; N, 11.19.

2-[3-(1*H*-Indol-3-yl)-*n*-propyl]-5,6-dimethyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (7oe, Table 2b, entry 13) : Light grey solid; m.p. 96 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 10.77 (1H, s, NH), 7.47 (1H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, Ar), 7.30 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar), 7.18 (2H, s, Ar), 7.11 (1H, s), 7.02 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar), 6.92 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar),

2.81–2.70 (4H, m), 2.23 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.13–2.06 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 154.2, 136.4, 129.2, 127.3, 122.4, 120.9, 118.4, 118.2, 114.1, 111.4, 28.5, 24.4, 20.0; IR (KBr) : 3409, 743 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₁N₃ : C, 79.17; H, 6.98; N, 13.85 and Found : C, 79.16; H, 6.97; N, 13.87.

5,6-Dichloro-2-methyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (7hp, Table 2b, entry 14) : Grey solid; m.p. 249 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.49 (1H, br s, NH), 7.69 (2H, s, Ar), 2.48 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 154.9, 123.9, 15.1; IR (KBr) : 3110, 1446, 1373, 1019, 859 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₈H₆Cl₂N₂ : C, 47.79; H, 3.01; Cl, 35.27; N, 13.93 and Found : C, 47.80; H, 3.01; Cl, 35.25; N, 13.93.

2-Benzyl-5,6-dimethyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (7qe, Table 2b, entry 15) : Greenish-brown solid; m.p. 104–105 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.29–7.26 (7H, m, Ar), 4.23 (2H, s), 2.35 (6H, s, Ar-CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 152.4, 136.3, 136.2, 131.6, 128.9, 128.9, 127.2, 114.8, 35.3, 20.2; IR (KBr) : 1636, 1463, 1444, 1422, 1313, 721 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₆N₂ : C, 81.32; H, 6.82; N, 11.85 and Found : C, 81.33; H, 6.83; N, 11.84.

Calculation of green metrics :

Calculations for the synthesis of 3-(1*H*-benzimidazol-2-yl)-1-piperidin-1-yl-propan-1-one (**5ad**)

Input		Output	
4-Oxo-4-piperidin-1-yl-butyric acid	1.85 g (10 mmol)	3-(1 <i>H</i> -Benzimidazol-2-yl)-1-piperidin-1-yl-propan-1-one	2.08 g
Benzene-1,2-diamine	1.08 g (10 mmol)	Alumina ball catalyst	0.29 g
Alumina ball catalyst	0.29 g (10% wt)	Total waste	0.29 g
Total	3.22 g		

E-factor :
 (0.29 g waste/2.08 g of product) = 0.14

Mass intensity :
 (3.22 g of raw materials used/2.08 g of crude product) = 1.55 (almost towards ideal result)

Atom economy :
 [257/(185 + 108)] × 100% = 88%

Fig. S1. The close-up SEM images of an activated alumina ball before calcination (99–175 nm particle aggregates), after calcination at 120 °C, 400 °C and 700 °C. The particle aggregates change shape from *spherical* to *rhombohedral* on calcination to 700 °C. The particle aggregate size also increases progressively on calcinations at 120 °C (614–818 nm aggregates), 400 °C (636–889 nm aggregates) and 700 °C (587–938 nm aggregates).

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